

Volume 9, Number 1, June, 2024

Geo-Studies Forum

An International Journal of Environmental & Policy Issues

*A Publication of the Department of Geography
and Environmental Management
University of Ilorin*

GEO-STUDIES FORUM

An International Journal of Environmental and Policy Issues

**Department of Geography and Environmental Management, Faculty of Social Sciences,
University of Ilorin, Nigeria**

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ASSESSMENT OF ADAPTIVE STRATEGIES EMPLOYED BY HERDERS IN THE PROVISION OF FODDER FOR LIVESTOCK IN THE GRAZING RESERVES OF NORTHEASTERN NIGERIA

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Abstract: *This research assessed adaptive strategies employed by herders in the provision of fodder for livestock in the grazing reserves of northeastern Nigeria. In northeastern Nigeria, livestock rearing system is being affected by scarcity of land and water resources. This inadequacy in the region arises from variations in agrarian relations, climate, and environmental deterioration. Such fluctuations create adaptive strategies for provision of fodder to livestock. Hence, this research work, assessed adaptive strategies employed by herders in the provision of fodder for livestock in the grazing reserves of northeast Nigeria. The objectives of this research work include, adaptive strategies employed, sustainable biodiversity management practices, preferred fodder for livestock and problems encountered in the provision of fodder. Semi-structured interview, focus group discussions (FGDs), field inventory and observations were adopted to generate data for the research. The major findings of the study revealed herders adapt to sedentary, use of resilient and tolerant livestock species, mixed livestock grazing and buying of supplementary feeds. Among the problems encountered in the grazing reserve were inadequate water resources, inadequate pasture, shortage of land, annual occurrence of conflict, uncontrolled bush fires, encroachment due to farming intensification, lack of security during mobility to some places, lack of funding and high cost in buying hay, competition of important grasses for livestock feeding and lack of fodder banks. The study concludes by emphasizing the need to critically address the problems encountered in the provision of fodder for livestock need to be address critically for the success and as a crucial requirement for better and sustainable grazing system. Proper monitoring and evaluation of the grazing reserves with the use of modern GIS facilities was recommended.*

Keywords: Adaptive Strategies; Fodder; Livestock; Grazing Reserves; Northeastern Nigeria

INTRODUCTION

Grazing Reserve is a piece of land that the government acquires, develops, and releases to the pastoral for grazing purpose (Iro, 2014). The Food and Agricultural Organization (FAO) (1975) defined Grazing Reserve as a vast natural landscape in the form of grass lands, shrub lands, woodlands, wetlands and deserts, managed by regulating the plant growth and livestock population overtime and space. A Grazing Reserve is also seen as natural landscape in the presence of native vegetation used for livestock grazing and by their management principally through the control of the number of animals grazing on them (Attang, 2014).

In Nigeria, the development of grazing reserves is a shared responsibility among Federal Government (70%), the State Government (20%) and the Local Government (10%) (Iro, 2014 and Aidonojie, Agbale & Ikubanni, 2021). The system is intended to encourage investment in land and to ensure its conservation through controlled grazing by limiting the number of animals entering a grazing land. The government gives each pastoralist in the grazing reserve a piece of land depending on the herd size and the carrying capacity of the land. The pastoralist in turn pays an annual rent to the Government as revenue for managing the reserve (Osano *et al.* 2013; Li *et al.* 2018).

The practice of proper grazing management dwells on the number of animals allowed to graze on a given reserve so that the existing vegetation is not depleted by overgrazing. Overgrazing of the vegetation reduces the production of forage, leads to soil sealing, reduced infiltration, high runoff, floods and erosion. These processes induce unfavorable changes in the botanical composition of the vegetation (Paul & Joseph, 2003). The potential for grazing reserve management depends on environmental factors such as, soil, topography, vegetation, location of the reserve, water availability and socio-economic characteristics of the local community (Hassan, 2016).

In Northeastern Nigeria, herding system has been affected due to the scarcity of land and water resources. The scarcity arises from changes in agrarian relations, climate change, and environmental decline. Such changes tend to create adaptive strategies for provision of fodder not to livestock (Gefu, 2008 and Egwu, 2016). With the increasing wave of scarcity of fodder in Northeastern Nigeria Grazing Reserves, this research work becomes imperative. This study aims to examine adaptive strategies in the provision of fodder for livestock, contextualized to focus on adaptive strategies employed, management practices, preferred fodder for livestock and problems encountered in the provision of fodder.

METHODOLOGY

STUDY AREA

Northeastern Nigeria, is located between latitudes 7°50' to 13°30' N and longitudes 9°50' to 15°00' E. It shares international boundaries with Niger and Chad Republic in the North and Cameroon in the East. It encompasses the states of Yobe, Borno, Bauchi, Adamawa, Gombe and Taraba (Figure 1). It covers an approximate land area of 208,105 km² representing about 22.53 % of Nigeria's total land area of 923,768 km². The region has an estimated population of 26 million in 2016 (National Bureau of Statistics, 2017). For effective coverage of the study area, sample areas were selected for detail studies based on ecological zones of the area (Figure 1), these include;

- i. In the Sahel savanna zone, Jakusko/Nasari grazing reserve (Jakusko area) and Badegana grazing reserve (Bursari area) both of Yobe State were selected.
- ii. For Sudan savanna zone, Yautare grazing reserve (Darazo area) of Bauchi and Kimba/Ritawa grazing reserve (Biu area) of Borno were selected.
- iii. In the Guinea savanna zone, Kirim and Mallum grazing reserves (Karim Lamido and Ardo Kola areas) of Taraba State were selected.
- iv. The other ecological zones of Montane and Lowland Forest have no grazing reserve.

The ecological zones, form the basis upon which the resources of the grazing reserves are based upon.

Source: Federal Ministry of Environment, (2019).
Figure 1: Study Area Showing Sampled Sites

DATA COLLECTION INSTRUMENTS

Semi-structured interview was administered to herders, to source information pertaining to adaptive strategies in the provision of fodder to livestock in the grazing reserves of northeast

Nigeria. Using Yamane (1967) sample size of 30% is sufficient, that makes 506 respondents in six grazing reserves. Hence, purposive sampling was used for selecting respondents in the study area (Table 1).

Table 1: Sampled of Respondents for Semi-Structured Interview

S/N	Grazing Reserve	Current Number of Herders	Number of Respondents ~ (30%)
1	Jakusko/Nasari	471	141
2	Badegana	290	87
3	Kimba/Ritawa	324	97
4	Yautare	320	96
5	Kirim	127	38
6	Mallum	156	47
	Total	1,688	506

Source: Field Survey, (2020).

FINDINGS & DISCUSSIONS

ADAPTIVE STRATEGIES EMPLOYED

Northeastern Nigeria undergoes different climate regime overtime, its temperature and rainfall changes annually and as such fodder production in its grazing reserves has reduced.

Fodder is one of the important ecological services for livestock feed. In order to bear the reduced fodder production, Table 2 presents findings on responses by herders through semi-structured interview schedule conducted in the field on adaptive strategies employed in the provision of fodder to livestock in the study

areas. Responses from the herders revealed that, 76.1% mobility as not important if there is enough quantity of fodder for livestock to feed on in the grazing reserve. In a similar study conducted by Momale (2014) in the Northwestern Nigeria, it was reported that over 60% of mobility was attributed to search for

feeds and grazing areas. He further stressed that the network for mobility permitted livestock to easily and freely move through the grazing routes from one geographical location to another without infringing on other forms of land uses particularly during the wet season cropping periods.

Table 2: Adaptive Strategies Employed in the Provision of Fodder to Livestock

Strategies	Important	Not Important	Total (%)
Mobility	23.9	76.1	100
Settling in one place (sedentary)	78	22	100
Use of resilient & tolerant livestock species	78.5	21.5	100
Mixed livestock grazing	70.5	29.5	100
Immigration	35	65	100
Through buying of supplementary feeds	64.6	35.4	100

Source: Fieldwork, (2021).

(N=506)

About 78% responded that they prepare settling in one place (sedentary). This finding is in accordance with National Livestock Transformation Plan (NLTP) (2019-2028), in its mandate to provide livelihood support in non-ranching options (grazing reserves). These include provision of routes for movements from one grazing reserve to another at seasonal changes, improve fodder production and provision of herder and farmer education system (National Economic Council, 2019).

To achieve the mandate of NLTP, high rate of livestock mobility has to be reduced as all ecological services will be rendered at ease cost. Although, none of the grazing reserve was provided with schools and it was revealed that herder's literacy was only accessible in few locations, mainly in farmers' settlement in Jakusko, Bursari, Gur, Yautare, Mallum Boyi and Lau. All these settlements are too far to most of the herders as children have to trek at least 7km by foot.

According to Onyekuru & Marchant (2014) scarcity do not just causes conflict, but if positive may leads to proper adaptation. This may lead to resilience, when a society depends on scarce natural resource, (water, pasture and agriculture) for their livelihoods, incidence of

climate change in conjunction with other anthropogenic variables will impact on human welfare by creating scarcity.

It was revealed that about 78.5% responses from the herders stated that the use of resilient and tolerant livestock species is important (Table 2). Knap & Doeschl-Wilson (2020) stated that infectious diseases reduce production performance, fertility and survival of livestock. This forms a limiting factor to the sustainability and profitability of livestock production. Hence, selection of diseases resilient and environmental tolerant livestock species is of utmost importance in terms of support cost and benefits. Anacleto *et al.* (2019) revealed that herd's resilience to diseases depends on adaptive capacity of the livestock in the herd, together with management decision that affect the performance and local environment of the livestock.

Majority of the herders (70.5%) responded that one of the most important adaptive strategies they practice is mixed livestock grazing. This grazing method is a combination of different species of livestock (camel, cattle, sheep, goat, donkey and horse) in a herd for grazing. This finding is in accordance with that of Hassan *et al.* (2018), in his research found that 86.6% of

the herders practice mixed livestock grazing in Janga Grazing Reserve. Also, Blanchet, Moeching & Hughes (2003) established that where large number of animals which are of different species graze, mixed grazing can be very helpful in pasture management and improved reserve health. They classified mixed grazing as when different types of livestock graze different plants. Two or more types of livestock graze at the same time, or follow one another through the pasture. Sheep, goats and cattle do not have the same grazing habits; this can be very helpful in pasture management. Sheep are more selective than cattle and tend to prefer grazing on forbs (broadleaved plants), but they will complement each other if grazed on pasture with a high proportion of forbs and browse. Multi-species grazing can benefit the livestock producer with better economic gains (different markets), predator protection, and improved reserve health.

As further revealed by the herder (65%), immigration is not an important adaptation strategy employed in the provision of fodder to livestock in the grazing reserves. However, with

the current security situation across West Africa it is advisable to stay sedentary as children need modern education. Findings from Momale (2014) revealed that vast majority of herders view least important for reason of migration implying that they no longer consider migration as a cultural practice that needs to be sustained. He emphasized that herders are more predisposed to permanent settlement, with short distance migrations. Most families had adopted sedentary lifestyles, while maintaining livestock mobility as a herd management strategy.

About 64.6% of herders indicated buying supplementary feed (Plate 1) as a form of adaptive strategies employed in the provision of fodder to livestock in the grazing reserve. Supplementary feeding will help herders to balance their livestock's diet for adequate nutrition that may be missing from their pastures. It is important to ensure that the whole diet of the livestock, including supplement and pasture is balanced to produce a healthy livestock. This is in accordance with NLTP (2019-2028) in its economic investment, supplementary feeding will be applied to ranching options.

Plate 1: Livestock Grazing with Supplementary Feeds near Badegana Grazing Reserve
Source: Fieldwork, (2021).

Due to scarcity of fodder in the grazing reserves of northeastern Nigeria, Table 3 shows herders FGDs on adopted grasses, shrubs and trees that

are available and serve as important for livestock feed based on their indigenous knowledge.

Table 3: Grasses, Shrubs and Trees Adopted for Provisions of Fodder to Livestock and their Indigenous Knowledge in the Grazing Reserves

Plant (Local & English) Name	Scientific Name	Indigenous Knowledge
<i>Daurawa</i> (African locust bean)	<i>Parkia biglobosa</i>	It seedlings, fruit pulp and the leaves are nutritious to browser livestock.
<i>Tafasa</i> (Senna sickle)	<i>Senna tora</i>	It increases the nutritional value of livestock feed.
<i>Tsintsiya</i> (Guinea grass)	<i>Megathyrsus maximus</i>	It is very nutritious, suitable for pasture and hay.
Elephant grass	<i>Pennisetum purpureum</i>	It serve as very important forage for camels and cattle, it can be stored as hay.
<i>Hantso</i> (Sap-wood)	<i>Monotes kerstingii</i>	It is used to treat dysentery and diarrhoea.
<i>Farin taramniyaa</i>	<i>Combretum glutinosum</i>	Serve as forage for browser livestock and use for treatment of intestinal worms, cough and impotence.
<i>Dengere</i> (Yellow trumpet)	<i>Costus spectabilis</i>	Use as fodder to sheep and goats.
<i>Fugore</i> (bottle gourd)	<i>Raphionacme brownie</i>	It is very nutritious and serves as supplementary feed for livestock.
<i>Karan giya</i>	<i>Cenchrus biflorus</i>	Valuable fodder plant for ruminants, at its early stages of development.

Source: Fieldwork, (2021).

SUSTAINABLE BIODIVERSITY MANAGEMENT PRACTICES

There is need to enforce every aspect of grazing policy developed on the management practices that will help the important fodder crops to remain healthy for sustainable biodiversity management. Based on the findings from the field, herders outline management practices that will help the grasses to remain healthy, these management practices include:

- a. Government and non-governmental organization's intervention on provision of improve variety of seeds of grasses as done during Petroleum Trust Fund Livestock Development Program.
- b. Combat grazing reserves to modern ranching system.
- c. Avoid frequent bush fires.
- d. Avoid taking long time grazing in one place practice control grazing.
- e. Adopt mixed livestock grazing system.
- f. Control of pest and weeds of fodder.

According to Bullock *et al.* (2011) one of the grazing management goals is to protect the quality of the pasturage against deterioration by overgrazing or to maintain the sustainability of the pasturage. Hassan *et al.* (2018) opined that proper land use and grazing management technique balances maintenance of forage and livestock production, this maintained biodiversity and ecosystem services. Studies

conducted by Kubkomawa & Kenneth (2018) revealed that the effect of improper grazing practices causes overgrazing, this further reduced pasture for livestock, stunted animal growth, desertification and erosion. Studies of Anderson & Hoffmann (2007) and Zhang *et al.* (2018) revealed that overgrazing changes vegetation structure and composition as a result of which some species increase in abundance and others decrease. Heavy grazing can change the composition of plant communities and also reduces ecosystem diversity of plants in poor soil.

Studies by McDonald *et al.* (2018) found that a number of ecological effects derive from grazing, and these may be either positive or negative. Negative effects of grazing (or more usually overgrazing) include increased soil erosion, adverse water quality impacts and loss of biodiversity. In some habitats, approximate levels of grazing may be effective in restoring or maintaining native grass and herb diversity in grazing reserve that has been disturbed by overgrazing, or by other human disturbance. Paul & Joseph (2003) stated that grazing

management practices centre on the number of livestock allowed to graze on a given reserve, along with proper grazing practices. The duration and season of their grazing are also considered. The stocking of a reserve must be carefully regulated so that the existing vegetation are not depleted or exhausted by overgrazing. Pfeiffer *et al.* (2019) revealed that overgrazing reduces the production of quality forage, exposes the soil to sealing, baking and erosion. It also reduces the infiltration of water into the soil, increases runoff, flooding and induces unfavorable changes in the botanical composition of the vegetation.

PREFERRED FODDER FOR LIVESTOCK

Table 4 are FGDs carried out to herders on preferred grasses, shrubs and trees that will serve as fodder to livestock in the grazing reserves. According to the highlight in National Livestock Transformation Plan (2019-2028) on the aspect of economic investment on non-ranching options (grazing reserves) to provide fodder crops through planting of seedlings of important forage. This will help in preventing farmer-herder conflict due to crop damage and lack of pasturage.

Table 4: Preferred Grasses, Shrubs and Trees for Livestock in the Grazing Reserves (GRs)

Plant Type	Local Name	Scientific Name	English Name
Grasses	<i>Hantso</i>	<i>Monotes kerstingii</i>	Sap-wood
	<i>Kayyari</i>	<i>Paspalidium distans</i>	Water crown grass
	<i>Ciyawar giwa</i>	<i>Pennisetum purpureum</i>	Elephant grass
	<i>Hardiya</i>	<i>Digitaria debilis</i>	Finger grass
	<i>Tsintsiya</i>	<i>Panicum maximum</i>	Guinea grass
	<i>Dengere</i>	<i>Costus spectabilis</i>	Yellow trumpet
	<i>Garraabal</i>	<i>Diheteropogon hagerupii</i>	
	<i>Gadagire</i>	<i>Alysicarpus vaginalis</i>	One-leaf clover
	<i>Fugore</i>	<i>Raphionacme brownie</i>	bottle gourd
	<i>Gude</i>	<i>Crateva religiosa</i>	Sacred garlic pear
Shrubs	<i>Gamba</i>	<i>Andropogon gayanus</i>	Gamba grass
	<i>Yakuwan daji</i>	<i>Hibiscus asper</i>	Bush Roselle
	<i>Alkaman tururuwa</i>	<i>Borreria stachydea</i>	Ant's wheat
Trees	<i>Kukumje</i>	<i>Maerua oblongifolia</i>	Necklace Berried Caper
	<i>Kuka</i>	<i>Adansonia digitata</i>	Baobab Tree
	<i>Dunduu</i>	<i>Dichrostachys cinerea</i>	Chinese lantern tree
	<i>Kokiya</i>	<i>Strychnos spinosa</i>	Natal orange

<i>Magariya</i>	<i>Ziziphus mauritiana</i>	Jujube
<i>Wuyan damo</i>	<i>Combretum molle</i>	Velvet bush willow
<i>Marike</i>	<i>Anogeissus leiocarpus</i>	African birch
<i>Duhuwa</i>	<i>Senegalia ataxacantha</i>	Flame thorn
<i>Ganki/ Zuwo</i>	<i>Celtis integrifolia</i>	African hackberry
<i>Banuri</i>	<i>Pterocarpus erinaceus</i>	African barwood
<i>Shabilabi</i>	<i>Boswellia odorata</i>	Frankincense tree
<i>Arrarrabi</i>	<i>Commiphora kerstingii</i>	Myrrh tree
<i>Kargo</i>	<i>Piliostigma thonningii</i>	Kameelspoor
<i>Sabara</i>	<i>Guiera senegalensis</i>	
<i>Jillaje</i>	<i>Acacia polyacantha</i>	White catch tree

Source: Fieldwork, (2021).

PROBLEMS ENCOUNTERED IN THE PROVISION OF FODDER

Fodder plays a central role in providing proper nutrition to livestock and in other way round providing livestock with sufficient quantity and quality of fodder is a critical issue due to improper management. Hence, findings from the study showcased the problems encountered in the provision of fodder to livestock in the GRs based on the FGDs from herders as follows;

- i. Farming intensification and shift in cropland leads to encroachment in to the GRs and routes.
- ii. Lack of security during mobility to some places.
- iii. Lack of funding and high cost in buying hay.
- iv. Competition of important grasses for livestock feeding.

- v. Lack of fodder storage facilities or banks to be used during early raining season.

Grazing reserve is a protected area which is solely use for livestock grazing. The research has revealed farming activities in the GRs (Plate 2 & 3). According to Manu *et al.* (2014) farmers encroachment on cattle routes is much more pronounced as farmers think that the grazing reserve is a preserve land, which government will convert to farmland in the future. Ahmed *et al.* (2002) revealed that most GRs and routes disappeared due to increasing settlements and cropping intensity. These are due to improper implementation of legal instrument to prevent encroachments. Umar (2002) stated that encroachment of cattle corridors and grazing lands by farmers are some of the major causes of conflicts between farmers and herders.

Source: Fieldwork, (2021).

Plate 2 & 3: Farming Activities in Mallum and Yautare GRs

Among the problems encountered in the provision of fodder to livestock in the grazing reserves is lack of security during mobility to some places in the FGDs carried out to herders. The constitution of federal republic of Nigeria mandated every leader to provide security of life

and properties of citizens as the pillar of leadership. The new bill on livestock includes justice and peace among the pillars of National Livestock Transformation Plan (2019-2028) to enhance coordination and accountability of security response. Dimelu *et al.* (2017) stated that

herders had the problems of insecurity of human and animal lives. Likewise, farmers had the problems of insecurity of human, farm products and buildings. These may cause displacement and economic losses leading to poor productivity to both farmers and herders.

Schlecht *et al.* (2020) revealed that movement of herds across various grazing reserves provides a beneficial outcome in terms of livestock nutrition and productivity. The growth of aboveground biomass will require year-round labor investment, and in the rural areas where seasonal migration is an important livelihood strategy, herding may suffer from absence of security. According to Hammed & Aminu (2021), herders can be both victims and actors of insecurity. This insecurity situation can be caused due to expansion of agricultural activities which reduced the availability of grazing areas.

Grazing reserves of northeastern Nigeria are facing drastic reduction of fodder crops due to many factors and as such there are shortages of pasturage to feed the livestock by herders. Shortages in rainfall, expansion in agricultural land and settlements leads to reduction in forage production. And as such, these has led to reduce number of livestock due to high cost of feed supplement by herders in the region.

The research revealed that competition of important grasses for livestock feeding as one of the problems encountered in the provision of fodder to livestock in the grazing reserves based on the FGDs from herders. According to Otte & Chilinda (2002) improvement in pasture is very expensive by individual and as such creates competition by livestock for available forage to make their nutritional requirement. Gupta *et al.* (2020) observed that competition of important grasses for livestock feed due to scarcity has created a problem to the livestock production system. This leads to reduced weight gain, decreased feed efficiency, poor condition and even death.

During field survey in the study area, none of the grazing reserves has a fodder bank as storage facility. Fodder bank are important requirements in the grazing reserves of northeastern Nigeria as fodder will dry and termites may eat up and destroy the remaining pasturage in the open grass field. As fodder does not have capacity for all round grazing, there is need for fodder storage facilities. The herders responded lack of fodder storage facilities as one of the problems encountered in the provision of fodder to livestock. According to Hanson & Ellis (2020) and Newell *et al.* (2021) improper or absence of fodder storage facilities has affected many herders in the grazing reserves of Sahel as climatic condition changes there is need to provide fodder storage facilities as constraint to adoption of climate resilient practice.

CONCLUSION

The research revealed that being a protected area to be solely used for livestock grazing by Grazing Reserves Law of 1965 has failed to accommodate the present realities on ground. In reality today herders use their local knowledge to promote livestock grazing through various adaptive strategies to provide fodder to livestock. Further, the problems encountered in the provision of fodder to livestock need to be addressed critically for the success and as a crucial requirement for better and sustainable grazing system. It was recommended that proper monitoring and evaluation of the grazing reserves using modern GIS tools and facilities. With the provision of well-trained personal on GIS technology by the government, there will be easier monitoring and evaluation on fodder crop yield across every grazing reserve. It will also help in protecting predators from harming livestock, controls various forms of encroachment by cultivation, settlement and illegal grazers. This will also improve the technical and managerial know how to managed the grazing reserves.

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